

The potential of e-fuels in the reduction of environmental footprint of a ferry

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Abstract

The shipping industry has for decades relied on fossil fuels, which have contributed significantly to global greenhouse gas emissions and other harmful emissions. Consequently, the decarbonization of this sector necessitates the replacement of conventional fuels with sustainable alternative fuels. This paper investigates the environmental performance of three e-fuels (e-LNG, e-methanol, and e-DME) for use in a ferry operating in the Adriatic Sea. A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology is employed to assess the environmental impacts of these e-fuels across key impact categories: climate change, acidification, and human toxicity. The e-fuels are compared with their fossil counterparts as well as diesel, the conventional fuel currently used by the vessel. The findings of the study indicate that e-LNG achieves 61% reduction of GHG emissions compared to LNG and 58% reduction compared to diesel. E-methanol and e-DME result in negative CO₂-eq emissions in the WTT phase, while in the TTW phase e-methanol generates low CO₂-eq emissions and e-DME remains at zero. E-fuels can be regarded as a promising alternative to conventional fuels, offering significant reductions in climate change impacts and contributing to lower levels of acidification and human toxicity.

Keywords: decarbonization; ferry; LCA; alternative fuels; e-fuels

1. Introduction

The maritime industry's dependence on fossil fuels is a major contributor to environmental degradation. Ships predominantly operate on Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) or Marine Diesel Oil (MDO), the combustion of which generates a range of emissions, including sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), Particulate Matter (PM), and Greenhouse Gases (GHGs) (Jovanović et al. 2022). While NO_x, SO_x, and PM are categorized as local pollutants directly affecting the environment and populations near shipping routes, GHG emissions present a global challenge. Decades of fossil fuel consumption have substantially increased atmospheric GHG concentrations, intensifying global warming and driving climate change. GHGs, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and fluorinated gases, create a barrier in the atmosphere that traps outgoing infrared radiation from the Earth's surface, causing the greenhouse effect (UNFCCC 2001).

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) estimates that shipping accounts for approximately 3% of global CO₂ emissions, a figure expected to rise with expanding global trade, highlighting the urgent need for decarbonization (IMO 2020). In response, the IMO's 2023 GHG Reduction Strategy outlines medium- and long-term initiatives, targeting a 20-30% reduction in annual GHG emissions and a 40% decrease in carbon intensity by 2030, compared to 2008 levels, while integrating zero or near-zero emission energy sources for at least 5% of energy consumption (IMO 2023). A crucial step towards mitigating emissions in the shipping sector is the transition from conventional marine fuels to alternative, cleaner energy sources. These alternatives include low-carbon fuels such as Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG), methanol, and Dimethyl Ether (DME), carbon-neutral options like biofuels, and zero-carbon fuels such as hydrogen, ammonia (Perčić et al. 2023). The slow adoption of alternative fuels is evident in the gradual increase in ships ordered with alternative fuel systems. LNG has emerged as the most widely adopted alternative fuel in the shipping sector, offering lower greenhouse gas emissions and significantly reducing SO_x, NO_x, and PM compared to conventional marine fuels. However, concerns regarding methane slip, high infrastructure costs, and limited bunkering availability present challenges to its widespread adoption. Methanol is another promising alternative, valued for its ability to reduce emissions and its compatibility with existing diesel infrastructure, allowing for

relatively straightforward implementation. Despite its lower energy density, methanol is increasingly used in various vessel types (Sjerić et al., 2025).

E-fuels, or electrofuels, have emerged as a pivotal technological pathway in the pursuit of deep decarbonization, particularly within hard-to-abate sectors such as shipping, aviation, and heavy industry. Unlike transitional options such as liquefied natural gas (LNG) or biofuels, e-fuels represent a long-term, carbon-neutral solution that integrates renewable electricity, hydrogen production, and carbon capture technologies. Fundamentally, e-fuels are synthesized by combining green hydrogen, produced through the electrolysis of water powered by renewable energy sources, with captured carbon dioxide (CO₂) or nitrogen (N₂), depending on the type of required fuel. Carbon-based e-fuels, including e-methanol, e-diesel, and e-LNG, are obtained through the hydrogenation of CO₂, whereas non-carbon-based e-fuels, such as e-ammonia and e-hydrogen, are produced by reacting green hydrogen with nitrogen extracted from the atmosphere (International Transport Forum Policy Papers, 2023).

The origin and sustainability of the CO₂ feedstock are crucial determinants of the overall climate neutrality of e-fuels. Renewable CO₂, captured either from biogenic sources or via Direct Air Capture (DAC) technologies, enables the establishment of a closed carbon cycle, wherein the CO₂ emitted during fuel combustion is offset by that removed during synthesis. Conversely, CO₂ captured from fossil-based industrial processes cannot be considered renewable, as it merely postpones the release of fossil carbon into the atmosphere and risks perpetuating dependency on fossil feedstocks (Nemmour et al., 2023; Roux et al., 2024). To achieve carbon neutrality, both the electricity used for hydrogen production and the carbon source must be renewable, ensuring that the entire life cycle, from feedstock acquisition to fuel combustion, results in a near-zero or even negative net carbon balance (eFuel Alliance, 2025).

Hydrogen generation through electrolysis is the cornerstone of e-fuel production. The main electrolyzer technologies, alkaline (AEC), proton exchange membrane (PEM), and solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOEC), vary in operational efficiency, cost structure, and technological maturity. Once produced, hydrogen serves as a key reactant in well-established industrial synthesis routes. The Fischer–Tropsch process yields e-diesel and e-kerosene, methanol synthesis produces e-methanol, and the Haber–Bosch process generates e-ammonia (Colelli et al., 2025). Among these, methanol and Fischer–Tropsch pathways are considered technologically mature, benefitting from existing petrochemical expertise and infrastructure, while e-ammonia and e-hydrogen are emerging alternatives offering high decarbonization potential but requiring new storage, handling, and safety frameworks (Bonardi et al., 2025).

The aim of this paper is to evaluate the environmental performance of three e-fuels (e-LNG, e-methanol, and e-DME) as potential alternatives to conventional marine fuels for a ferry operating in the Adriatic Sea. Using an LCA approach, the paper assesses the environmental impacts of these e-fuels across different impact categories, i.e. climate change, acidification, and human toxicity. By comparing the results with fossil-based counterparts and conventional diesel, the paper highlights the potential of e-fuels to contribute to the decarbonization of the shipping sector.

2. Literature review

The decarbonization potential of e-fuels in maritime transport has been extensively investigated. Lindstad et al. (2021) analyzed the feasibility, energy use, and GHG reduction potential of various e-fuels for shipping and concluded that, under favorable renewable electricity scenarios, e-methanol could reduce well-to-wake (WTW) emissions by up to 99%, while e-LNG could achieve reductions of 88% (dual-fuel Otto engines) or 98% (dual-fuel Diesel engines) relative to Marine Gas Oil (MGO). Similarly, Dettner and Hilpert (2023) assessed the life-cycle performance of e-methanol as a marine fuel and found that full substitution of conventional fuels with e-methanol could cut emissions by approximately 50% by 2030 and up to 90% by 2040, assuming adequate renewable energy supply and effective carbon pricing mechanisms. In a comprehensive LCA of nine alternative marine fuel pathways, Lee et al. (2024) demonstrated that e-methanol and e-ammonia can achieve greenhouse gas reductions of 88.2% and 86.6%, respectively, although their economic feasibility remains constrained by production costs. Zincir and Arslanoglu (2024) conducted a comparative LCA of 14 alternative marine fuels, identifying e-methanol and e-Fischer–Tropsch diesel as exhibiting the lowest overall environmental burdens across multiple impact categories. Ingwersen et al. (2025) performed a prospective LCA comparing the environmental impacts of e-ammonia, e-Fischer–Tropsch diesel,

e-methanol, and e-LNG. Among the assessed pathways, e-methanol achieves a GHG reduction of 81% compared to very low sulphur fuel oil (VLSFO), but it also shows the highest human toxicity impacts. In contrast, e-LNG exhibits the lowest GHG reduction (73%) among the assessed e-fuels, yet it achieves the lowest acidification levels. Ha et al. (2026) show that while e-LNG can achieve substantially lower well-to-tank (WTT) emissions when produced entirely from renewable electricity, its overall climate benefits remain limited by methane slip in the tank-to-wake (TTW) phase. This finding is consistent with Comer et al. (2022), who concluded that both methane slip and upstream methane leakage dominate the life-cycle emissions of e-LNG, constraining its mitigation potential in the marine sector even under fully renewable scenarios. Likewise, Mukherjee et al. (2023) evaluated the techno-economic feasibility of four renewable marine fuels, methanol, dimethyl ether (DME), LNG, and bio-oil, produced through biomass or CO₂-based pathways, concluding that DAC-derived fuels are currently cost-prohibitive, while e-methanol and e-DME based on industrial point-source CO₂ capture represent more viable near-term options under moderate carbon taxation regimes.

Despite their environmental advantages, e-fuels are characterized by high energy intensity and complex production chains. WTW analyses indicate that their total primary energy requirements can be up to six times greater than those of fossil fuels, largely due to conversion losses in electrolysis, CO₂ capture, and fuel synthesis (Lindstad et al., 2021). Nonetheless, when powered entirely by renewable energy, e-fuels can achieve near-complete carbon neutrality and serve as a critical complement to electrification in sectors where battery-electric or direct hydrogen propulsion systems remain impractical. Yılbaşı (2025) emphasized the necessity of adopting holistic WTW frameworks in life-cycle evaluations, arguing that conventional TTW approaches underestimate upstream emissions associated with feedstock generation and energy conversion.

Economic feasibility remains the most significant barrier to widespread e-fuel adoption. Current production costs for e-kerosene and e-methanol range from €1,200 to €4,200 per tonne, driven primarily by the high capital expenditure of electrolyzers and CO₂ capture units, as well as the cost of renewable electricity (Colelli et al., 2025). Achieving cost competitiveness will depend on technological learning, large-scale deployment, and continued declines in renewable electricity prices. Policy instruments such as Contracts for Difference (CfDs), Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), and carbon pricing are essential to close the price gap between e-fuels and fossil fuels. The European Union (EU) has positioned itself as a global leader in promoting e-fuels through the Green Deal and Fit-for-55 framework. The Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) establishes binding targets for renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs), while ReFuelEU Aviation and FuelEU Maritime regulations introduce mandatory blending requirements for sustainable fuels such as e-kerosene, e-methanol, and e-ammonia (Colelli et al., 2025). Complementary financial mechanisms, including the Innovation Fund and the European Hydrogen Bank, aim to support early-stage deployment and mitigate investment risks associated with large-scale production facilities.

Beyond Europe, other major economies are also advancing e-fuel development. The United States supports low-carbon fuel production through tax incentives under the Inflation Reduction Act and Bipartisan Infrastructure Law, while Australia's Hydrogen Headstart Program and Renewable Energy Zones leverage abundant solar and wind resources to develop export-oriented hydrogen and e-fuel industries (Colelli et al., 2025). Nevertheless, large-scale deployment will necessitate massive expansion of renewable power generation capacity, potentially several terawatts globally, to meet the combined demand for hydrogen and carbon feedstock (Lindstad et al., 2021). This requirement raises important questions about the optimal allocation of renewable electricity across direct electrification, hydrogen production, and synthetic fuel synthesis to maximize overall emission reductions.

Technological progress continues to improve the efficiency and scalability of e-fuels. Innovations in solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOECs), advanced catalysts, and integrated process designs are enhancing energy conversion efficiency while reducing operational costs. Furthermore, coupling e-fuel production with carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) systems could yield negative-emission fuels when biogenic CO₂ is employed as a feedstock (Bonardi et al., 2025). Despite these advances, cost parity with fossil fuels is unlikely to be achieved before the 2040s, underscoring the need for consistent policy support, long-term investment frameworks, and cross-sectoral coordination.

Based on these findings, the existing literature provides the theoretical basis for understanding how different e-fuels perform across the WTW framework in maritime applications. Prior studies consistently demonstrate that WTW emissions depend primarily on the carbon intensity of electricity, the origin of CO₂ feedstock and methane slip in the case of e-LNG. Although existing LCAs mostly target GHG emissions, the broader analyses available point to differences in other impact categories,

such as toxicity and acidification. These studies identify the key factors and methodological choices that determine life-cycle results for emerging marine e-fuels.

Through the literature review, several clear limitations remain:

- Literature lacks regional route-specific LCAs, even though route-specific factors can influence WTW emissions.
- Existing studies approach e-fuels using different assumptions, such as the source of electricity and CO₂ feedstock, which makes direct comparison of e-fuels difficult.
- LCA studies on e-DME in maritime settings are almost entirely missing, representing one of the most significant gaps in the current literature.
- Limited number of studies incorporate multiple impact categories, which reduces the ability to assess impacts beyond climate change.

This study addresses these gaps in several important ways:

- It incorporates a real vessel operating on a specific regional route (Split-Vis), directly responding to the lack of route-based LCAs.
- It applies the same WTW framework to all three e-fuels (e-methanol, e-LNG and e-DME), addressing the different assumptions used in earlier studies and allowing a consistent comparison across fuels.
- It includes e-DME, for which maritime LCA studies are nearly non-existent.
- It incorporates multiple impact categories, such as climate change, acidification and human toxicity, providing a broader environmental perspective than most existing LCAs.

3. Methodology

3.1. Illustrative example

The selected ferry operates on the longest ferry route in Croatia, transporting passengers and vehicles between the city of Split and the island of Vis, Fig. 1. Its technical specifications are given in Tab. 1. A one-way trip covers a distance of 56 km (30.2 NM) and typically takes 140 minutes. The ferry's schedule varies between the high season and the off-season, with an average of 800 round trips per year.

Fig. 1. Analysed ferry (Croatian register of ships 2025; Jadrolinija 2025).

Tab. 1. Ferry's technical data (Croatian register of ships 2025; Jadrolinija 2025).

Ship name	Oliver
Length, L (m)	108
Breadth, B (m)	17.5
Draught, T (m)	4.4
Main engine power, P_{ME} (kW)	2x3972
Auxiliary engine power, P_{AE} (kW)	2x618
Design speed, v_{de} (kn)	18.7

Ships are typically designed to operate at speeds, v_{de} (kn), that corresponds to 70%–90% of the main engine's load capacity. However, actual operating speeds can vary due to factors such as weather conditions, adherence to schedules, voluntary speed reductions and other operational considerations. Using data on the route length, l (km), and the corresponding travel duration, t (h), the service speed of

the ship, v_s (kn), can be determined. By following up the cubic relationship between ship speed and power, the average main engine power, $P_{ME,ave}$ (kW), was calculated according to the following equation (Perčić et al., 2020):

$$P_{ME,ave} = (P_{ME} \cdot 0.85) \cdot \left(\frac{v_s}{v_{de}}\right)^3. \quad (1)$$

Assuming the auxiliary engine operates at an average load of 50%, denoted as $P_{AE,ave}$ (kW), the total average power of the ship, P_{ave} (kW), is determined by adding $P_{ME,ave}$ and $P_{AE,ave}$. The energy demand for each alternative power system is assumed to be equivalent to that of the existing diesel-powered vessel. The energy consumption per distance of the existing diesel-powered ship (EC) is then calculated according to:

$$EC = \frac{P_{ave}}{v_s}. \quad (2)$$

The energy needs and EC for each different power system configuration installed on the existing ship are equal to those for the existing diesel-powered ship. The fuel consumption per distance (FCD) of the ship is calculated by multiplying EC with the specific fuel consumption (SFC), such as in the equation:

$$FC = EC \cdot SFC. \quad (3)$$

3.2. LCA

LCA is a methodology used to analyze the environmental footprint of a product, process, or system throughout its entire life span. Leading LCA standard ISO 14040 (International Organization for Standardization, 2024) provides a framework and requirements which mainly focus on the process of performing the LCA which, among other things, require the definition of the goal and the scope of the assessment, the functional unit, the system boundary and the life-cycle inventory. In the maritime sector, LCA provides a framework for quantifying emissions associated with fuel pathways, from initial feedstock extraction to combustion onboard ships (Blanco-Davis and Zhou 2014). The assessment of different ship power systems is typically conducted using the well-to-wheel LCA methodology, a widely recognized standard in transportation-related studies. However, in shipping applications, this framework is adapted as the Well-to-Wake (WTW) model, which is divided into two key phases: Well-to-Tank (WTT) and Tank-to-Wake (TTW), Fig. 2. The WTT phase considers all processes related to feedstock extraction, fuel production, and distribution, whereas the TTW phase focuses on emissions released during vessel operation.

Fig. 2. The system boundary of the performed LCA.

The emissions from the WTT phase were calculated using the LCA software GREET 2024 (GREET 2024). The WTT phase of diesel fuel includes extraction of crude oil and its transportation by tanker over a distance of 4,000 km to the Croatian refinery where it is processed into diesel. After that, diesel is distributed by tank trucks over 300 km to the port's fuelling station. Methanol and LNG are used in dual-fuel engines, where diesel serves as the pilot fuel in a share of 5%. Both WTT and TTW phases are considered for both the main and pilot fuels. In the case of methanol, production occurs through steam reforming of natural gas at a facility in Egypt. The methanol is then transported by tanker over 3,000 km to Croatia, followed by an additional 300 km delivery by tank trucks to the refuelling

stations. The WTT phase of LNG involves natural gas extraction in Qatar, where it undergoes liquefaction on-site before being transported approximately 8,000 km to Croatia. In contrast to LNG and methanol, DME is assumed to be used in a modified Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) rather than a dual-fuel engine. Its WTT phase includes production through the dehydration of methanol, with the transportation process referring to the transport via tank-trucks over a distance of 1,500 km to the port (Perčić et al. 2023).

The pathways for producing e-fuels are fully obtained from the GREET 2024 software, where gaseous hydrogen, renewable electricity, and CO₂ from DAC are used for e-fuel production. Since e-LNG requires liquefaction, an all-electric liquefaction process powered exclusively by renewable energy is assumed to maintain the low-carbon nature of the e-fuel production pathway. Similarly, methanol dehydration into DME is also considered to be fully electrified, utilizing renewable energy sources. The transportation processes for e-fuels are assumed to be the same as those of their fossil counterparts, as both fuels share similar physical and chemical properties, requiring no significant modifications to existing distribution and storage infrastructure.

The TTW phase refers to the ship's operational stage, during which fuel combustion generates exhaust emissions. These emissions are determined by using emission factors obtained from (Perčić et al. 2023). The TTW emissions from the combustion of e-fuels are assumed to be identical to those of their fossil counterparts, as both share the same chemical composition and combustion characteristics. However, CO₂ emissions from combustion are not accounted for, given the carbon neutrality of the investigated e-fuels. Tab. 2 summarizes life cycle inventory for all investigated fuels.

Tab. 2. Life cycle inventory for all investigated fuels (GREET, 2024)

Fuel	CO ₂ source	Hydrogen source	Production pathway	Electricity source	Transport distance	Engine type
Diesel	Fossil crude oil	-	Refining	Grid mix	4000 km tanker + 300 km truck	Diesel engine
LNG	Fossil natural gas	-	Liquefaction at origin	Grid mix	8000 km LNG carrier	Dual-fuel
Methanol	Natural gas	-	Steam reforming + methanol synthesis	Grid mix	3000 km tanker + 300 km truck	Dual-fuel
DME	Fossil methanol	-	Methanol dehydration	Grid mix	1500 km truck	Modified ICE
e-LNG	Direct air capture	Renewable electrolysis	Methanation + liquefaction	100% renewable electricity	Same as fossil LNG	Dual-fuel
e-methanol	Direct air capture	Renewable electrolysis	CO ₂ hydrogenation	100% renewable electricity	Same as fossil methanol	Dual-fuel
e-DME	Direct air capture	Renewable electrolysis	E-methanol dehydration to DME	100% renewable electricity	Same as fossil DME	Modified ICE

In this paper, different emissions obtained by performing LCA are used to quantify emissions that contribute to various environmental impact categories. Specifically, the analysis focuses on climate change, acidification, and human toxicity. These impacts are evaluated through the calculation of Global Warming Potential (*GWP*), Acidification Potential (*AP*), and Aerosol Formation Potential (*AFP*), providing a comprehensive understanding of the environmental footprint associated with the investigated fuels. Climate change is driven by the accumulation of GHGs in the atmosphere. Each of these gases has its overall contribution to global temperature rise. *GWP* metric standardizes these effects by expressing emissions in terms of CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq) over a 100-year horizon, and it is calculated by the following equation (Perčić et al., 2022):

$$GWP = 1 \cdot E_{CO_2} + 36 \cdot E_{CH_4} + 298 \cdot E_{N_2O}, \quad (4)$$

where E represents the emitted quantity of a specific gas.

In addition to climate change, shipping emissions can also have negative effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems through acidification and eutrophication. The release of sulfur oxides (SOx) and nitrogen oxides (NOx) leads to the formation of acidic compounds in the atmosphere, which subsequently deposit onto land and water surfaces through precipitation in the form of acid rain, snow, or mist. This process disrupts soil and water chemistry, depleting nutrients and harming biodiversity (Kim and Chae 2016). AP is a key environmental indicator used to quantify these effects, expressed in sulfur dioxide equivalents (SO₂-eq). It is calculated by applying SO₂-equivalence factors to the emissions of acidifying gases, where NOx has a factor of 0.7 and SOx a factor of 1, as shown in the following equation (Perčić et al., 2022):

$$AP = 1 \cdot E_{SOx} + 0.7 \cdot E_{NOx}. \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, emissions of SOx, NOx, and PM contribute to aerosol formation, which poses significant risks to human health by increasing respiratory diseases and reducing air quality. AFP quantifies these impacts and is calculated by applying PM_{2.5}-equivalence factors to the relevant emission sources, where PM₁₀ has a factor of 0.5, SOx a factor of 0.54, and NOx a factor of 0.88 (Perčić et al. 2022):

$$AFP = 0.5 \cdot E_{PM10} + 0.54 \cdot E_{SOx} + 0.88 \cdot E_{NOx}. \quad (6)$$

4. Results and discussion

The LCA assessed WTT and TTW emissions per km. Based on these data, indicators for various environmental impact categories are calculated and presented in Fig. 3, 4, and 5. In the following results, D denotes diesel, M represents a methanol-powered ship, and e-M refers to e-methanol.

Fig. 3. LCA results of different ship power systems (impact category: climate change).

The ship power system with the highest emissions is the LNG-powered vessel. Although LNG has a lower carbon content than diesel, its overall climate impact is significantly influenced by CH₄ emission, which has a much higher impact on climate change than CO₂ over 100 years, making even small quantities of unburned methane, known as methane slip, a critical factor in LNG's total emissions profile. This methane slip occurs during combustion in marine engines, as well as during LNG

handling and transportation, leading to higher CO₂-eq emissions compared to conventional fuels. Compared to fossil LNG, e-LNG achieves a 61% reduction in GHG emissions, while it results in a 58% reduction compared to a diesel-powered ship. However, e-LNG still exhibits higher emissions than other e-fuels due to the energy-intensive processes required for its cryogenic storage and long-distance transportation with specialized LNG carriers, as well as the methane released during its combustion, which further contributes to its overall carbon footprint.

The other considered e-fuels, e-methanol and e-DME, result in negative CO₂-eq emissions in the WTT phase due to their production process, which utilizes renewable CO₂ as a feedstock. As a result, these fuels contribute to a net reduction in atmospheric CO₂ levels, effectively leading to negative emissions. Additionally, the use of renewable hydrogen derived from electrolysis powered by renewable energy further eliminates fossil-derived emissions, enhancing the overall carbon-negative effect. The production of e-DME involves the synthesis of e-methanol followed by its dehydration to form e-DME. This process contributes to a greater reduction in GHGs in the WTT phase, as e-DME benefits from both the carbon incorporation during e-methanol production and conversion to e-DME, resulting in a more effective utilization of captured CO₂ than e-methanol alone. Since e-DME is used exclusively in modified ICE, while e-methanol operates in a dual-fuel engine with a small share of pilot diesel, e-methanol generates low CO₂-eq emissions in the TTW phase, whereas e-DME remains at zero. As a result, the total *GWP* of e-DME remains negative, making it the fuel with the lowest *GWP* among the investigated options.

Fig. 4. LCA results of different ship power systems (impact category: acidification).

Fig. 5. LCA results of different ship power systems (impact category: human toxicity).

Regarding both *AP* and *AFP*, e-fuels demonstrate a reduction in emissions compared to a diesel-powered ship, which exhibits the highest values due to significant SO_x, NO_x, and PM emissions during combustion. In contrast, use of LNG (both in its fossil and e-fuel forms) demonstrates a lower impact on acidification and human toxicity among the fuels considered. This can be attributed to its higher net calorific value (NCV), Tab. 3, which results in lower fuel consumption per unit of energy delivered compared to DME and methanol, thereby reducing the overall emission impact per kilometer.

Tab. 3. Net calorific value of analysed fuels (GREET, 2024; Lindstad, 2021)

Fuel	NCV, MJ/kg
D	42.7
LNG	49.2
e-LNG	49.2
M	19.9
e-M	19.9
DME	28.8
e-DME	28.8

The performed LCA showed that e-fuels produced with CO₂ obtained from DAC result in low *GWP* because the CO₂ from their combustion is not taken into account. While DAC offers the advantage of large-scale, location-independent CO₂ extraction, it remains a less mature technology with higher energy demands due to the lower CO₂ concentration in ambient air compared to industrial gases. In contrast, capturing CO₂ from large industrial sources, such as plants or power stations, is a well-established process that is currently more feasible and cost-effective, even if it may not be the most sustainable long-term solution (Mukherjee et al. 2023). In Fig. 6, the *GWP* comparison of different e-fuels with CO₂ originating from DAC and the cement industry is presented.

Fig. 6. Comparison of GWP of e-fuels for different CO₂ origins.

According to the comparison in Figure 6, e-fuels are more sustainable when produced with CO₂ from DAC. However, when produced from CO₂ captured from cement plant emissions, e-methanol emerges as the most environmentally friendly option compared to the other investigated fuels. The cement industry was selected as a relevant industrial source due to its global significance and emission profile. The cement industry is currently responsible for approximately 7% of global and 4% of EU CO₂ emissions (Marmier, 2023).

Lindstad et al. (2021) provides a global strategic assessment of various e-fuels, evaluating their GHG reduction potential, energy use, and cost using a WTW methodology. This study, in contrast, brings a detailed LCA of e-LNG, e-methanol, and e-DME for a specific ferry operating in the Adriatic Sea, focusing on climate change, acidification, and human toxicity. Both studies highlight the promise of e-methanol and e-DME, though e-LNG poses challenges due to methane slip and high energy demands.

A critical aspect that complements the environmental assessment of e-fuels is their price and market availability, both of which strongly influence their near-term feasibility in the maritime sector. Current production costs of e-fuels remain significantly higher than those of fossil fuels due to the energy intensity of electrolysis, CO₂ capture, and synthesis processes. According to Lindstad et al. (2021) and Colelli et al. (2025), production costs for e-methanol and e-LNG currently range from €1,200 to €4,200 per tonne, depending on electricity prices, electrolyzer efficiency, and CO₂ source. Mukherjee et al. (2023) also highlighted that e-DME, derived through methanol dehydration, exhibits slightly lower synthesis costs but is still far from commercial competitiveness without policy support. In comparison, fossil-based LNG and methanol typically cost between €400–900 per tonne, underscoring a two- to fourfold cost disparity. Availability remains limited as e-fuel production is still in its pilot and early demonstration phase, with only small-scale facilities in operation across Europe, Japan, and the United States. Large-scale e-methanol plants, such as those announced by Maersk and European Energy, aim to deliver the first commercial volumes by the late 2020s, while e-LNG projects remain in the feasibility stage due to high liquefaction energy demand and methane leakage concerns (eFuel Alliance, 2025). Conversely, e-DME has attracted industrial interest because it can be synthesized via simpler catalytic routes from methanol and stored using existing LPG infrastructure (Nemmour et al., 2023). Overall, while e-methanol and e-DME are technologically mature and logistically compatible with current maritime infrastructure, their economic viability hinges on reductions in renewable electricity prices, technological scaling, and sustained policy incentives such as the EU's FuelEU Maritime regulation. In the short term, e-fuels will likely occupy niche markets, gradually expanding as production costs decline and renewable energy capacity increases.

Although this study provides detailed, route-specific insights, the findings are limited by the use of a single ferry as the case study. The results may not be directly generalizable to other vessel types, sizes, or operational profiles, as fuel consumption, engine performance, and emission patterns can vary significantly across ship classes and routes. In addition, assumptions related to fuel availability, future infrastructure development, and regional electricity mixes introduce uncertainty into the life cycle modelling. Therefore, while the case study offers valuable indicative trends, broader fleet-level assessments are required for more comprehensive conclusions.

5. Conclusions

This study evaluated the environmental performance of three electro fuels - e-LNG, e-methanol, and e-DME - as potential substitutes for conventional marine fuels for a ferry operating in the Adriatic Sea. Using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, the analysis covered key environmental impact categories, including climate change, acidification, and human toxicity. The results clearly demonstrate that the use of e-fuels can significantly mitigate the environmental footprint of maritime operations when produced from renewable CO₂ and powered by green electricity.

The findings indicate that while all three investigated e-fuels contribute to the decarbonization of shipping, their environmental performance and practicality vary. The most significant conclusions of this study are:

- E-DME showed the lowest Global Warming Potential (*GWP*) among the fuels considered, achieving even negative well-to-tank emissions due to the efficient utilization of captured CO₂.
- E-methanol also demonstrated strong environmental benefits, emerging as a near-term viable solution thanks to its technological maturity and compatibility with existing dual-fuel systems.
- E-LNG achieved moderate reductions in GHG emissions but remains less favourable due to methane slip during combustion and high energy requirements for liquefaction and storage.
- All investigated e-fuels showed substantial reductions in acidification and human toxicity compared to conventional diesel, confirming their potential to improve air quality and reduce health-related impacts.

Despite the promising environmental performance, economic feasibility remains the primary barrier to large-scale adoption. The production costs of e-fuels are still two to four times higher than those of their fossil-based counterparts, largely due to the high costs of electrolysis, CO₂ capture, and renewable electricity. Moreover, current global production capacity is limited, with most e-fuel projects still in demonstration or pilot stages. Broader deployment will require technological scaling, lower renewable energy prices, and consistent policy support through mechanisms such as FuelEU Maritime and carbon pricing frameworks.

Upcoming IMO regulatory measures are expected to strongly influence the real-world adoption of e-fuels in maritime transport. The IMO's 2023 GHG Strategy introduces progressively stricter carbon-intensity requirements and encourages the uptake of zero- and near-zero-emission fuels. Complementary regional policies, such as the EU FuelEU Maritime regulation, will impose GHG intensity limits on energy used onboard, directly favouring e-methanol, e-DME, and other e-fuels with very low WTW emissions. These regulatory developments are likely to accelerate investment in renewable hydrogen and CO₂-based fuel production, expand bunkering infrastructure, and promote early adoption of e-fuels on short-sea and passenger routes, such as those in the Adriatic Sea.

In summary, e-fuels represent a realistic long-term pathway toward achieving carbon neutrality in maritime transport. Among them, e-methanol and e-DME stand out as the most practical short- to mid-term solutions for decarbonizing short-sea shipping, offering both environmental and operational advantages. Future research should integrate techno-economic analysis with LCA to evaluate environmental-economic trade-offs and identify optimal strategies for sustainable maritime fuel transition.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [Ivana Jovanović], upon reasonable request.

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